

MULTIGRADE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS: BEST PRACTICES IN TEACHING IP STUDENTS

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Multigrade Elementary School Teachers: Best Practices in Teaching IP Students

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Abstract

This phenomenological study explored the best teaching practices, challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights of multi-grade teachers assigned in the six different indigenous schools in Talaingod, Davao del Norte, Philippines. An in-depth interview was conducted with the six teachers of Gatong Elementary School, Igang Elementary School, Napunong Elementary School, Naseco Integrated School, Ibuyag Lamburan Elementary School, and Lambid Elementary School. The thematic analysis revealed that the teachers' best practices organizing students into groups, differentiated instruction, translating lessons to the local language, indigenizing lessons, positive reinforcement, discovery approach, heterogeneous grouping, and activity integration. They also incorporated self-invented best teaching practices such as talk to me, atong ginikanan atong katimbayayong sa kaalam (AGAKK), gabay sa pagbasa, and gabay sa kaalaman, science intervention material, drive reading intervention or drive program, and Friday karaoke session. Their challenges included language barriers and lack of resources, facilities, and contextualized materials. Their coping mechanisms were proper time management, seeking stakeholder's help, language translation, introducing games, discovering new strategies, and thinking positively. Teachers shared their valuable insights about cultural sensitivity to IP learners, resourcefulness, and passion to provide substantial education despite cultural and language barriers to students, and teachers' presence and providing quality education to indigenous students are of paramount significance. Training on teaching strategies, lesson planning, instructional materials development, and capacitating school heads must be administered. Hence, the study recommended that government and education sectors' support is vital to address the emerging problems of the multi-grade teaching approach and the indigenous schools and to realize the envisioned quality education in rural communities.

Keywords: *multigrade teaching, indigenous students, best teaching practices, challenges, phenomenological study*

Introduction

Today, the multigrade approach in teaching is widely applied in remote schools of Davao del Norte, where indigenous people reside, because it has a limited enrollment number and lack of school facilities. However, increasing issues concern the need for pedagogical training for teachers handling multigrade classes. Different local teaching practices have been incorporated and conceptualized in their teaching strategies to give students a substantial education.

In South Africa, issues regarding multigrade teaching have been widely discussed because of its potential to enhance the country's teaching quality, specifically in geographically and socioeconomically disadvantaged schools. However, most of their education materials and teacher training are designed for single-grade classrooms, which hinders multigrade schools from being less competitive and lacking skills development. South Africa emphasized the need for global efforts to transform pedagogic practices and develop guidelines to capacitate multigrade teachers towards a multigrade approach (Joubert, 2010).

A study conducted in Zamboanga del Sur, Philippines, shows that despite various challenges in rural schools, multigrade teachers employ different teaching practices such as Collaborative Learning, Classroom Management, Connecting Teaching to Real-life Situations, Differentiated Instruction, Teacher Flexibility, and Integrating Technology to enhance student abilities and make them competitive learners. It suggests that multigrade teaching is highly effective and beneficial when the best teaching practices are applied (Naparan, 2021).

In Talaingod District, Division of Davao del Norte, the school population comprises different indigenous students, and their form of education practices the multigrade teaching approach. Multigrade teaching is crucial in these schools because teachers must travel and walk for hours to arrive at their designated schools, teachers have difficulty understanding the students due to different cultural upbringing, the language used by both teachers and learners varies from each other, and the class lessons range from English, Filipino, and mother tongue, which is Bisaya. More so, multigrade teachers face immense challenges due to a lack of proper training in handling multigrade classroom dynamics, as their professional knowledge and preparatory degrees are only centered on handling monograde classes.

With this, the proponent came up with the idea of doing an in-depth exploration of the insights, challenges, coping mechanisms, and best teaching practices utilized by multigrade teachers assigned in different local areas of Talaingod District to give us a clearer perspective on how teachers and indigenous students co-exist in a multigrade environment with the other language used in verbal communication and learning materials.

Research Questions

The study intended to discover teacher's experiences and best teaching practices in a multigrade classroom situated in an indigenous

community. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What are the best practices of teachers in multigrade elementary schools?
2. What are the challenges of elementary multigrade teachers?
3. What are the coping mechanisms of elementary multigrade teachers?
4. What are the insights of teachers in this multigrade teaching situation?
5. What programs can be crafted from the study's findings about the best practices of multigrade teachers in teaching IP students?

Literature Review

Historical Background of Multigrade Teaching in the Philippines

To ensure that education is available to all people, 164 members of the United Nations have signed a global commitment to implement multigrade education. Teaching multiple grade levels in rural locations with fewer students enrolled in each grade level is standard practice. According to Section 1997 of DepEd Order No. 96, the number of students in each class must be between eight and 35 at all times (Cornish, 2021).

The Multigrade Program in the Philippine Education System was introduced in 1993. Through the DECS Order No. 38, series of 1993, known as "improving access to elementary education by providing complete grade level in all public elementary schools through a combination of multigrade classes." It has contributed substantially to the Philippine Department of Education's efforts to democratize access to education while maintaining quality in roughly 19% of the country's public elementary schools in far-flung, marginalized, underserved, and poor rural communities. The multigrade program could provide a workable answer to the problem of overcoming educational obstacles such as access and inclusion. This allows teachers to empower and engage their students by giving them various learning opportunities (SEAMEO Regional Center for Educational Innovation and Technology, 2020).

The Philippines has adopted the multigrade teaching strategy because it is cost-effective for increasing student engagement rates and academic attainment in rural schools. Children have a greater propensity to participate in class when they are offered a variety of activities to complete alongside children of different grade levels. To develop students' full potential for learning, teachers construct learning activities and performance assignments and then encourage students to engage in those activities in various relevant ways (Saraspe & Abocejo, 2020).

Multigrade Teaching Approach

The multigrade teaching approach is a form of education in which a single instructor is accountable for instructing students of many grade levels inside the same classroom. The organizational pattern of a multigrade classroom differs from that of the standard classroom organization pattern because the classroom compromises several grade levels (Berry, 2010). This strategy has firm attempts to provide children access to universal primary education, wherein the teacher serves as the primary mediator of the teaching and learning process (Ramathan & Mzimela, 2016).

Multigrade Teachers Challenges

Newly appointed teachers working in multigrade classrooms face more significant challenges than their counterparts in schools with independent classes (Oral, 2014). Practices with multigrades demand a strategy distinct from those used in classrooms that are epistemologically and methodologically autonomous (Boix, 2020). According to Quail and Smyth (2014), teaching multiple grade levels at once can be perceived as complex because the educator has to adapt the instructional materials and activities, they use to meet the requirements of students of varying ages and grade levels. From the educators' standpoint, this method places a significant amount of responsibility on the educator throughout the "planning, execution, and assessment of teaching" process (Hyry-Beihammer & Hascher, 2015).

Many teachers in rural regions lack the necessary training and are unfamiliar with the most recent teaching methods and strategies. Teaching multiple grades presents both a difficulty and a chance for professional growth. For teaching in multigrade classes, a teacher's professional growth, knowledge, and skills are all crucial (Du Plessis and Mestry, 2019).

Multigrade Teaching Practices

As the number of multigrade courses expands globally, particularly in developing nations, it is imperative that the arrangements and confirms essential to guarantee that quality teaching occurs in this environment are in place (Hargreaves, 2001).

According to some research findings, multigrade teachers engage in contextualized teaching in their classrooms to encourage student learning. They did this by providing particular instructions to the students, which helped them connect the teachings they were teaching to the student's actual life scenarios. This explicit Instruction explains and models the material directly to the students (Reutzell, 2014).

Based on the study conducted by Sali and Arriola (2019) in Basilan, Philippines, the methods of multigrade instructors may include the inclusion of information technology (IT) into resources and facilities, the detection of student deficits to place them in the appropriate remedial classes, or the cross-posting of learner potential and skills. Organization and administration of the classroom that

is founded on the initiative of a former teacher but is appropriately observed. Mentoring and action research are forms of instructional practice for overcoming various obstacles, as well as revisions to the evaluation assessment tool.

Classroom Management in Multigrade System

It refers to the process of overseeing and conducting everyday operations of a classroom. This also entails preparing the teaching environment and ensuring it is kept in a reasonable condition to meet educational objectives. It establishes expectations in an organized school setting, including routines, rules, and penalties (Savage & Savage, 2010).

Instructional Material in Multigrade System

Instructional materials are paramount in teaching and learning at all levels of education. More instructional materials can lead to uninteresting and unengaging class sessions. Audiovisual and electronic teaching materials such as radio, tape recorder, television, and videotape recorder, together with traditional instructional materials such as books, charts, and maps, contribute significantly to making learning more stimulating (Atkinson, 2000).

Indigenous People Communities

The indigenous people of the Philippines comprise 14% of the total population in the country. These communities are part of the most vulnerable sector, which is economically deprived and has underprivileged socioeconomic standing. They are known to have increasing literacy, unemployment, and poverty rates in comparison to the other groups of the population in the country. The IP settlements are generally found in remote locations; they lack access to basic facilities and have a disproportionately significant chance of illness, death, and nutritional deficiency (De Vera, 2007).

Education in Indigenous Communities

A more recent estimate by the United Nations Development Programme (2010) placed the number of indigenous people in the Philippines between 14 and 17 million. These people belong to approximately 111 different ethnic groups, and 33% are primarily concentrated in the northern region of Luzon and 61% in the southern region of Mindanao.

In the Philippines, its education system practices formal education that expects individuals to receive continuous learning in academic institutions from elementary, secondary, and tertiary levels (Hanusek & Woessman, 2010). The Philippine Department of Education ensures that all Filipinos receive an equal opportunity to access free education, specifically at the elementary level. To meet this objective, they created elementary schools in all barangays (Romo, 2021). The DepEd established The Indigenous Peoples Education (IPEd) Program as a way to address Indigenous Peoples' (IP) entitlement to primary education that recognizes their identities and promotes the worth of their indigenous knowledge, abilities, and other components of their cultural custom (Department of Education, 2016).

Teaching Multigrade among IP Students

Indigenous Peoples typically have limited access to education overall, and the education that they do receive is of lower quality. The common problem is that their education frequently does not include curriculum or teaching practices that acknowledge the cultures, histories, local languages, pedagogies, and traditional knowledge of their communities (Wodon & Cosentino, 2019). Various factors influence the failure to deliver education to indigenous communities. Some of these are lack of connection between school and indigenous community, lack of lesson contextualization, lack of understanding of the indigenous mode of learning, lack of integration of indigenous cultural values, and lack of understanding of the support system of indigenous learners (Garcia-Alix, 2008). Added by Adonis (2021) cited by Magdadaro & Sacramento (2022), the formal education indicated by an established societal norm must meet IP learners' urgent and specific requirements.

Cornelio and de Castro (2016) state that several issues must be addressed, including the discrimination that indigenous peoples' children and teenagers experience. This is due to the cultural insensitivity of the educational setting in which they are educated, and the educational methods mandated by the national education curriculum. Moreover, when teaching in an environment with several grade levels, teachers often struggle to create an environment favorable to learning, mainly where most of the instructors formally instruct indigenous students who are not of indigenous descent (Panuncillo, 2016).

Methodology

This section provided the concept of the methods used in this phenomenological study. It consisted of the type of research design, the setting, the role of the researcher, the participants, the data gathering procedure, data analysis, the credibility of the study, and the confidentiality statement and ethical matters for the research participants.

Participants

Participants were selected using purposive sampling, enabling the researcher to choose those most relevant to the study's goal based on her discretion. Six multigrade teachers from six different Talaingod, Davao del Norte schools were chosen for face-to-face, In-Depth Interview Focus based on their availability and professional background. Among these participants were teachers who had won

district, division, and regional awards. Criteria for selection included having taught multigrade elementary classrooms for at least three years, being situated in indigenous communities, not belonging to the Ata Manobo tribe, and willingness to share knowledge and experiences related to the study's topic.

Instruments

In this qualitative study, a one-on-one in-depth interview (IDI) was used to gather the information needed. The researcher first made sure that her interview guide was approved by the panel members before conducting the interview. The questions were aimed to investigate the elementary multigrade teachers' best teaching practices, challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights into their experiences in educating indigenous students. Moreover, to make sure that every detail was noted throughout the interviews, a recorder application was employed.

Procedure

Data collection involved a series of interrelated activities to gather good information to answer research questions. In this research, the researcher considered Talaingod the focused locale area because it was where the proponent worked. It was relevant to the topic as this municipality had handled a multigrade teaching approach in its education system, and its students were part of the Ata Manobo community. The research participants were intentionally chosen based on the criteria stipulated above. These participants were expected to give the best information that satisfied the objective of this study.

In phenomenological research, the data collection process involves rigorous searching of different sources of evidence. The proponent specifically employed an In-Depth Interview for this research. An interview guide was prepared prior to the In-Depth Interview proper, which was used to generate information from the participants. These questionnaires underwent interview question validation to ensure the results' accuracy and alignment with the subject being explored. To record the data being gathered, the researcher used a voice recorder application on a mobile phone for the entire interview process.

Additionally, the researcher used the transcribed interview to identify themes from the participants' answers. It was employed to create a more coherent approach to the phenomenon. Yin (2003) asserts that one critical tactic would be categorizing problems inside each lived experience, which was subjected to searching for common themes that reflect the phenomenon. The interpreted data were supported by different literature to ensure its credibility and reliability.

Ethical Considerations

The research study adhered to a rigorous code of ethics throughout the data collection process. Ethical approval was obtained from the thesis adviser, and permission was secured from the Schools Division Superintendent before informing District Supervisors and School Heads. Participants were invited to participate voluntarily, with the assurance of freedom to withdraw without repercussions. Informed consent was obtained, detailing the study's goals, significance, and confidentiality measures. Participant safety was prioritized through anonymity and data protection protocols. Confidentiality was maintained, and participants were assured of privacy during interviews. Additionally, the study underwent a plagiarism check to ensure reliability and honesty.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings of the research questions during the data-gathering process. The research questions specifically address the best practices, challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights of multigrade teachers assigned to primary schools where indigenous students are. With these research questions, the goal of this study which is to explore how these multigrade teachers provide quality education to an indigenous community regardless of multigrade teaching and socio-cultural differences, is realized.

What are the best practices of teachers in multigrade elementary schools?

The first major research question is, '*What are teacher's best practices for in multigrade elementary schools?*' There are five specific research questions under this major research question.

1.1 Best Teaching Practices Employed for Students to Understand Lesson

The themes discussed in this section were based on the first specific research question 1.1 'What best teaching practices do you employ for students to understand your lesson?' From the responses, five themes were identified: Organize Students into Groups, Consideration of Language Differences of Students, Use of Differentiated Instruction, Translate Lessons to Local Language, and Indigenization of Lessons.

One of the themes that are apparent best practices, according to the teachers, are the indigenization of lessons. For the lessons to be effectively delivered in the classroom, the teachers use visualizable examples within the local community. The scenarios, things, and events in indigenizing lessons should reflect the community's life.

Participant 6 strongly shares this claim;

In my experience in the field, especially since I started at this school, my students are really pure IP, I really need to find a way so that

they can relate to my other lessons. Like in terms of giving examples, I will really use things or events that they can see and experience there in their IP community. The lessons should be contextualized and then indigenized based on the things present in their community. And there are lessons that really seem to be given extra effort to explain. They really need some methods to visualize what you are talking about, through pictures.

Incorporating Atong Ginikanan Atong Katambayayong sa Kaalam (AGAKK), Gabay sa Pagbasa and Gabay sa Kaalaman in Teaching were three teaching practices employed by the teachers during pandemic to provide students with education despite the modular learning approach. It is one of their intervention programs to ensure that students' can understand their lesson effectively.

Here's participant 1 has to say;

In terms of Interventions, I have Talk to me, AGAKK, Gabay sa Pagbasa, Gabay sa Kaalaman.

She further explained the meaning of each intervention;

There is a difference between Gabay sa Kaalaman and Gabay sa Pagbasa because we cannot really teach our students directly. During that opening of modular printed, Gatong was the pilot school who will implement the distance learning modality. What we did was I proposed the Gabay sa Kaalaman intervention-it is more into teaching; teachers are reading from this distance and the students are on the other area. So, teachers are using microphones and rechargeable speakers.

1.2 Best Strategies for Students' Class Participation

This section presents the findings of the second specific research question, 1.2 'What are the best strategies you use for students to have class participation during lectures?' From the first major question, 'What are the best practices of teachers in multigrade elementary schools?' the themes accumulated in this specific research question are: Use of Positive Reinforcement and Use of Discovery Approach.

One of the themes that emerges in this question is the Discovery Approach, wherein students will be given time and freedom to speak out their ideas during the classes. By allowing students to discover the topics independently, they can be more engaged in it. Too often, they raise questions because they become more curious about the lessons being discussed. Allowing them to be hands-on in their activities can make class participation more visible because everyone has room to explore.

Participant 6 says;

If it is a discovery approach, let them discover what is wrong with the corrective instruction while you are having the corrective instruction you are letting your student discover what you want to get from them. What do you want to teach to them because that is where they can construct the way you throw your questions.

Additionally, Participant 1, a multigrade awardee in region 11 due to her efforts in doing multigrade focused interventions and programs for Mathematics, MAPEH, and Reading. Her interventions are Friday Karaoke Session and Talk to Me.

She has this to say;

What I did during that time is that I designed lots of programs for my learners in terms of reading and mathematics. I remember I designed interventions, I let them have videoke every Friday because it is like you are hitting two birds in one stone, you are teaching MAPEH, and teach reading. It is a good reading intervention. They will talk in front of the mirror. I have there a mirror where they can talk with themselves.

1.3 Best Ways for Students' Unity and Collaboration

This section will discuss the findings from the third specific question, 1.3 'What are the best ways for students to have unity and collaboration in a multigrade classroom?' The themes gathered for this specific question are Grouping Students Heterogeneously, Introduce Activities Students Can Relate to, Giving Goals for the Day, and Assign Individual Tasks to Students.

One of the themes gathered is Grouping Students Heterogeneously. For them, organizing students into different learning groups in terms of skills, intelligence level, and learning style is an effective mode to enhance unity in a multigrade classroom. In heterogeneous grouping, students with diverse academic performance and social skills are combined in one group to work collaboratively on learning tasks.

Here is Participants 1 side;

So, in grouping I usually design my grouping with multiple intelligence. So, in one group there is a fast learner, average, and what is called not very advanced. Another thing to have the collaboration is tasking, one is the leader, one is secretary, and one is a member or keeper of the things after the activity. In that way they know their rules, then they can function already during the group activity because they have already identified rules, and they already knew what are the things that are expected from them during the group activity.

1.4 Motivation to Continue Teaching

This part will discuss the result of the fourth specific question, 1.4 What motivates you to continue teaching in a multigrade classroom? The evident themes are Having a Passion for Teaching, More Opportunities to Help Each Other, Motivated with Challenges in Teaching Multigrade, Children becoming more Mature, Motivated to Help Students, Motivated by Eagerness of Students.

1.5 Takeaway as Multi awarded Teacher in Multigrade

This section presents the findings to the specific research question 1.5 'What does it takes to be awarded as a multi-awarded teacher in multigrade?' The following themes from this specific question are Doing Multiple Tasks and Responsibilities, Doing What Needs to be Done, and having a Very Fulfilling Experience.

2. What are the challenges of elementary multigrade teachers?

For the second major question, 'What are the challenges of elementary multigrade teachers?' the participant's personal challenges, problems faced in using the instructional material, and personal points on the areas that need improvement while teaching in an indigenous people with a multigrade classroom are being explored.

2.1 Difficulties Encountered in Teaching Indigenous Multigrade Classroom

The themes acquired from the participants answer the first specific question; 'What are the difficulties you encountered in teaching an indigenous multigrade classroom?' Under the second major question, 'What are the challenges of elementary multigrade teachers?' The themes were the following: Language Barrier, Limited Human Resources, Limited Resources and Facilities, Difficulty with Bridging Local Dialect to Reading.

One of the themes here is the Language Barrier. Teaching in an indigenous community is a challenging task. Aside from the fact that they have to blend different grade levels, they too have to adjust in terms of language usage because most of these teachers speak Bisaya, and their students have their own native language different from them. Therefore, teachers find it vital to acquire even a little knowledge of the learner's dialect to incorporate it during classes. Teachers must ask the students to translate some words, and it is beneficial both for students and teachers to understand each other while learning each other's languages.

Participant 2 shares her point of view;

Number 1 is the dialect, as a teacher in the IP community, you should know the language of your learner. Although you are not as into it, at least you understand, you have words that can be easily understood by the natives, they are happy ma'am when you use the words in their native language.

Participant 4 share the same stand;

Language barrier is the number 1, I think they will understand if they understand Bisaya, and I think they are learning to understand Bisaya.

2.2 Problems Faced in Using Instructional Materials

This section will discuss the themes accumulated from the second specific question, 2.2 What are the problems you faced in using the instructional materials while teaching in an indigenous multigrade classroom? Under the second major question, 'What are the problems you faced in using the instructional materials while teaching in an indigenous multigrade classroom?' The themes yielded are Problem with Contextualized Materials, Problem with Electricity, and No Problem with ICT.

2.3 Areas Needing Improvement

This section will discuss the themes apparent in the third specific question, 2.3 What are the areas/things that need improvement in your multigrade classroom? Under the second major question, what are the problems you faced in using the instructional materials while teaching in an indigenous multigrade classroom? The emerging themes are More Spacious Classroom, Problem with Chairs and Tables, and More Time to Prepare IMs.

3. What are the coping mechanisms of elementary multigrade teachers?

The findings for the third major question, 'What are the coping mechanisms of elementary multigrade teachers?' is presented in this section. In this part, there are three specific questions wherein the participants share their ways of coping with the different struggles they have faced as multigrade teachers in the community.

3.1 Ways Used in Handling Challenges Encountered

This section answers the first specific question; 'How did you handle the challenges you encountered in teaching an indigenous multigrade classroom?' under the third major question 'What are the coping mechanisms of elementary multigrade teachers?' The themes produced are Proper Time Management, Seek Help from Stakeholders, Translate Language through Tagalog or Bisaya, Introduce Games, Enjoy the Moment and Discover New Strategies, and By Thinking Positive.

Seeking help from stakeholders is a crucial step in addressing school problems effectively. Due to limited resources, the teachers there opt to seek help from proper departments and government agencies to address their problems. Opening up to the stakeholders is vital for them to address their problems in the school. Involving stakeholders in this situation fosters a sense of shared responsibility within the community.

Participant 2 strongly said;

Of course, number 1 ma'am, let us ask for support from our stakeholders, come to them, do not be shy to ask for help because if we keep quiet, they do not know about our needs, we need to be open as to what we need. For instance, we tap the LGU for our school in the stage, we do not have a stage, so we tap the LGU that we need a stage, we wrote a letter for the LGU, and they help us.

3.2 Most Effective Strategy in Teaching Indigenous Multigrade Classroom

This section addresses the second specific question, 3.2. 'Among these strategies you employed, which one is the most effective strategy you face in teaching an indigenous multigrade classroom?' Under the third major question, 'What are the coping mechanisms of elementary multigrade teachers?' The themes here are Thinking Positively and Planning in Advance, Reach Out to Stakeholders, Peer Tutoring, Introducing Games, Positive Reinforcement, and Proper Mind Setting.

Peer tutoring is another effective strategy to solve the problem in terms of language barriers. In peer tutoring, teachers have support because someone will substitute for her students when teaching a particular language.

Participant 3 says;

The peer tutoring, little teacher because the peer tutoring knows that you can translate, you can explain to him what the meaning of such words is as they usually use their native language.

3.3 Most Convenient Thing Inside the Classroom

This section answers the third specific question, 3.3 What are the most convenient inside the classroom? Under the third major question, 'What are the coping mechanisms of elementary multigrade teachers?' Saving Old Instructional Materials, Being Resourceful, Peer Tutoring, Assigning Little Teacher, Positive Reinforcement, and Utilization of IMs.

Assigning a little teacher is a convenient method because these littles assist the teacher and maintain a positive classroom environment. The teacher can rely on them because they are the ones who will provide additional support to their classmates in understanding complex topics and tasks. These little teachers can also assist teachers in distributing materials, managing classroom routines, and preparing activities.

Here's participant 4 side;

If it is convenient, I will be able to take a break, I would say the little teacher, so I can take a break for a while.

4. What are the insights of teachers in this multigrade teaching situation?

The discussion in this section talks about the fourth major question; 'What are the insights of teachers in this multigrade teaching situation?' Four specific questions fall under this major question, providing teachers with personal learnings while teaching in a multigrade class situated in an indigenous community.

4.1 Advice to Fellow Multigrade Teachers

Here are answers to the first specific question, 4.1 'Based on your experiences, what advice can you give your fellow multigrade teachers?' The themes formulated here are Attend Training on Multigrade Classrooms, Seek Help from Seasoned Multigrade Teachers, Make Own Learners as Motivation, Understand and Love Learners' Culture, To be more Patient, and Love the Teaching Profession.

One of the themes formulated here is Attend Training on Multigrade Classrooms. Multigrade teachers would like to extend their advice to new multigrade teachers to attend training related to this teaching approach. These awarded and promoted multigrade teachers are just new to this kind of education approach and started from scratch, but they equip themselves through constant training. There are improvements in their teaching strategies when applied in their classroom as they expose themselves to different pieces of training and seminars.

Participant 1's sentiment;

I have been a multigrade teacher for 6 years. Your hardwork will pay you off. I was promoted masters in a very small school. I ask my mentor I really want to have a training because I really want to know. The training really helps me a lot to improve and then the experience itself. Expose yourself with training and apply what you have learned from the training. We need to apply the trainings to the real-life setting.

4.2 Multigrade Teachers' Call to the Government

This section addresses the second specific question, 4.2. 'Based on your experiences, what do you want the government to know about your situation?' This seeks to allow teachers to voice out their needs to the government to create a sustainable and convenient education for schools located in mountain areas and for teachers assigned to multigrade classes. The themes gathered here are Allowance for Multigrade Teachers, More Budget for Facilities, Provide More Materials for Learners, More Multigrade Teachers, Assign Ads to Small Schools, and Provide More Funds.

One of the themes gathered from the participants is Provide More Materials for Learners. The teachers want the government to understand the difference between monograde and multigrade in order for them to be aware of the different instructional needs for both educational approaches. In their case, they are provided with materials like the monograde. However, this will not work efficiently in their cases because unlike monograde, which handles only one grade level, multigrade, on the other hand, has yet to produce two to three different instructional materials to suffice the needs of these three grade levels in the class.

Participant 2 confessed;

The government should understand what the differences about the mono are and multigrade Multigrade teaching is facing children with different levels, as a multigrade teacher we must provide the needs of our learner depending on their level of ability.

4.3 Learning Gained as Multigrade Teacher in Indigenous Community

This section highlights the third specific question; 'Based on your experiences, what are your learnings in being a multigrade teacher assigned in an indigenous community?' This discusses multigrade teachers' lessons acquired within the whole years they served as teachers in an indigenous community. The themes garnered here are Presence of Teacher Needed in IP Communities, A Challenge and a Blessing as a Multigrade Teacher, A Sense of Fulfillment in Being a Multigrade Teacher, Being a Multigrade Teacher Calls for Resourcefulness, Learn to Love the Children, Lowland Learners more Privileged.

One of the gathered themes is the Presence of Teacher Needed in IP Communities. Upon setting foot in the IP community, the teacher realized that a lack of education was evident. The presence of teachers in an IP community is of utmost urgency and necessity because these communities are not just economically underprivileged but uneducated as well. Most of the parents there has no writing and reading literacy. Teachers assigned in this community have to exert extra effort to provide education to the students and their parents. For the IP community, their teachers are pillars of hope for them to reach their individual aspirations.

Participant 3 conveyed;

They are miserable when there is no teacher will dare to teach in their place, because there are parents who do not know how to read, do not know how to write, so they will grow up not knowing that. It is important that when you are in the community, you can think about what you will do as a teacher for preparation or so that you can give to them and help them in their situation.

4.4 Possible Training Programs to Address Challenges in Multigrade Classroom

This section will address that fourth specific question 4.4; 'Based on your experiences, what are the possible training programs that should be implemented to address the challenges in the multigrade classroom?' The themes are Training on Teaching Strategies, Training to Capacitate School Heads, Training on Lesson Planning, and Training on Development of Instructional Materials.

The Training of Teaching Strategies is one of those themes mentioned above. The teachers assigned to an indigenous community have witnessed that their culture is far different from the cultures exercised in lowland areas. Upon observing them, they realized that the teaching methods they used were not of par effectivity because they had witnessed that the culture of the indigenous communities is far different from the cultures exercised in lowland areas. Therefore, training programs that will enhance their teaching strategies in accordance with IP learners' culture and tradition must necessarily be implemented. It will enhance their teaching competency, thus providing more quality education to the learners.

Participant 6 explained;

Possible training programs, training programs on how to teach teaching strategies in multigrade classes then more information about their culture and tradition because there are some students who stops going to class because they marry and some are in child labor, it is just that, it is just a different competency, and it should be improved.

The best practices applied by multigrade teachers to help their students understand their lessons were organizing students into groups (mixed ability group), considering students' language differences, using differentiated instruction (corrective instruction), translating lessons to local language, and indigenizing lessons.

Additionally, these teachers shared the keys to being multi-awarded winners in the multigrade teaching category. They must do multiple tasks and responsibilities all at once, putting effort into accomplishing necessary assignments, thus giving them a fulfilling experience. Their multigrade class interventions such as Talk to Me, Atong Ginikanan Atong Katimbayayong sa Kaalam (AGAKK), Gabay sa Pagbasa, and Gabay sa Kaalaman, Science Intervention Material, Drive Reading Intervention or Drive Program, and Friday Karaoke

Session were of paramount significance in their accomplishments as multigrade teacher awardee because it improves the learning competency of their students.

The strategies mentioned above were considered their best practices in delivering good quality education to the indigenous students at multigrade elementary schools. Academic interventions vary based on the needs and abilities of their students. It is crucial to implement effective intervention measures to assist students in enhancing their academic ability by identifying their areas of weakness (Syed Yahya et al., 2021). Intervention strategies are a series of actions for fostering development in a particular area where students need more improvement. It aids students in the value of the knowledge they learn from their classroom (Lazowski et al., 2016).

These multigrade teachers faced various challenges in their careers in the highlands. For instance, they had trouble teaching indigenous multigrade classrooms due to language barriers, limited human resources, limited resources, facilities, and bridging local dialects to reading. Language barriers are psychological obstacles wherein language functions as a psychological device that influences the process of communication (Vygotsky, 1978, as cited by Da Costa & Fernando, 2021). The presence of language barriers impedes efficient communication, hence impacting the process of teaching (Da Costa & Fernando, 2021).

The physical space and structure of a classroom substantially influence students' learning experience. An appropriately constructed educational setting should possess ample space and the capacity to accommodate diverse educational activities (Rashid, 2023). Moreover, the classroom arrangement should be structured in a manner that effectively reduces distractions and interruptions, facilitating students' concentration on their educational tasks and thus improving learning acquisition (Soudijn et al., 2018).

Multigrade teachers ensured that despite their everyday struggles in the class, they found ways to cope with it in their ways, such as incorporating proper time management, seeking help from stakeholders, translating language through Tagalog or Bisaya, introducing games, enjoying the moment, and discover new strategies, and by thinking positive. Of all these strategies, thinking positively, planning, reaching out to stakeholders, peer tutoring, introducing games, positive reinforcement, and proper mind setting were the most effective while saving old instructional materials, being resourceful, peer tutoring, assigning little teacher, positive reinforcement, and utilization of instructional materials were the most convenient.

According to Naparan and Alinsug (2021), many multigrade teachers in the Philippines associate activities in their classes based on the ability and skills of their student learners. Studies show that incorporating games in teaching students enriches student participation, boosts academic performance, enhances social and emotional learning, and forces students to keep pushing learning (Nguyen, 2021). Acquiring the ability to be optimistic can help one deal with stress or setbacks, overcome failure in certain situations, and increase self-efficacy and resilience (Smida et al., 2021).

The multigrade teachers' experiences have had them share significant advice with their fellow multigrade teachers in the indigenous communities, such as equipping themselves through attending training about multigrade classrooms, seeking help from seasoned multigrade teachers, making their learners as motivation, understanding, and love learners' culture, to be more patient, and love the teaching profession. It is essential to provide training and enhance teachers' knowledge, skills, and teaching abilities in multigrade pedagogy.

The teaching profession extends beyond merely disseminating factual information from teachers to students inside the classroom. These teachers must commit both their intellectual and emotional faculties to survive. Indeed, teachers are essential to the indigenous community because their expertise will enrich students' education quality. Educational authorities must ensure the provision of essential teacher training and development resources. This would enable educators to enhance their pedagogical skills and effectively impart knowledge to their indigenous students (Suarta et al., 2022).

Possible training programs to address challenges in multigrade classrooms are training on teaching strategies, training to capacitate school heads, training on lesson planning, and training on developing instructional materials. Several studies, such as (Schütze et al., 2017; Supriatna, 2021 & Ulla, 2017), have pointed to the significance of teacher training as a crucial solution to problems in the educational system. Saira et al. (2021), educators with extensive training are better equipped to instruct students effectively. Training is a systematic procedure to acquire competencies in a specific field. It strengthens educators' pedagogical abilities and instructional strategies, which can be effectively employed to enhance students' academic performance (Ulla, 2018).

Conclusion

This study discusses the practices, challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights of multigrade teachers in the Talaingod, Davao del Norte indigenous community. After comprehensive thematic analysis and discussion with supporting literature, the researcher has gathered substantial conclusions about this topic. While it is significant to recognize the education sectors' provision of primary education in rural and far-flung communities, one cannot deny that various improvements must be implemented to achieve the goals of providing primary education to learners. The different practices and self-improvised interventions administered by multigrade teachers in Talaingod, Davao del Norte, are evidence that the education sector lacks adequate support for the ongoing challenges these teachers face. While multigrade teachers' coping mechanisms can be viewed as a resilient action towards addressing their educational problem in the mountains, it is considered reliable proof that support from the education and the government sector is vitally crucial to lessen their struggles and substantiate their resilience.

Additionally, teachers and indigenous students are struggling and facing this inequality and lack of support. The teaching and learning process will be significantly and continuously disturbed once insufficient and ineffective solutions will increase in the long run. Moreover, this study concludes that indigenous-based education must be centered on acquiring the quality education this country envisions. The principles of their education must be a combination of a modernized approach and contextualized learning based on their culture, knowledge, language, and teaching traditions for them to survive in the demands of the current time while enriching their own indigenous identity—which will allow them to blend both in the global and local worlds.

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